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Determination of delamination onset in composite laminates by application of acoustic emission

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SUMMARY: This paper presents the results of the experimental investigations of the free edge delamination in curved glass fibre/epoxy composite laminates loaded in bending. A set of static four-point bending tests was carried out on 32-ply curved beams with $(0_4/\pm 45_6)_s$ stacking sequence. The specimens were all fitted with strain gauges on both inner and outer radii at the centre of the curved section. In addition, a broadband acoustic emission transducer was mounted on the top surface of the specimen. All specimens failed suddenly with no prior visible damage. Failure occurred at the uppermost interface between the 0 plies and the ± 45 plies in all cases. The loading, strain gauge readings and the AE signals were successfully recorded during the course of each test. Detailed analysis of the measured parameters has been performed allowing determination of the onset of the delamination process that led to macroscopic failure. The onset of delamination has been clearly depicted by the change in the AE hits, counts and amplitude recorded throughout the course of the test. The obtained results show high consistency. On average the delamination initiates at 96% of the maximum load. The experimental results show that AE hits, counts and amplitude describe the damage initiation process very well in this case. Based on the results presented in this paper the conclusion can be drawn that the delamination onset in composite laminates can be successfully determined by application of acoustic emission.

KEYWORDS: Composite Laminate, Delamination, Free Edge, Acoustic Emission

INTRODUCTION

Delamination between plies in composite laminates is one of the commonly observed failure modes. One source of delamination is laminate edge, where high interlaminar stresses are developed. The stress transfer between plies at the free edge is accomplished through the action of interlaminar stresses in order to satisfy the equilibrium equations of the laminate. The stress field at the free edge is three-dimensional and singular. Many authors have studied the problem and there are a large number of papers addressing the topic. Pipes and Pagano [1] approached the problem by calculating the change in the stress distributions at the free edge through the application of classical elasticity theory. Recently, a comprehensive book on the interlaminar stresses and damage mechanics has been written by Herakovich [2].

Stress based failure prediction criteria do not give satisfactory results due to stress singularity. The normal fracture mechanics approach cannot be used because the strain energy release rate increases with the crack length and does not reach an asymptotic value. An improved fracture mechanics approach that is based on an assumed initial defect gives good prediction of failure load. The accuracy of prediction depends on the size of the assumed defect [3]. In order to overcome that problem a new approach involving the acoustic emission testing is being proposed.

Within the scope of work described in this paper acoustic emission testing is applied for determination of delamination onset. Acoustic emission (AE) monitoring is one of the best tools for following the dynamics of internal damage [4]. The AE monitoring applied in testing of structural components expands the scope of traditionally used parameters and enables determination of critical loading or damage mechanisms in cases where application of other methods is difficult or impossible. The AE testing is well-established NDT method however the interpretation of the signals still brings many challenges and opportunities [5]. In case of damage mechanism that leads to sudden catastrophic failure in the structural component AE

brings on the information on damage onset and progression. This information is then used to characterise the fracture mechanism and to develop the prediction method.

EXPERIMENT

A set of five specimens was subject of static four-point bending tests carried out on 32-ply curved beam specimens with $(0_4/\pm 45_6)_S$ lay-up. Hexcel Composites (former Ciba) Fibredux 913G-E-5-30 pre-preg was laid up by hand over a steel tool. Vacuum consolidation was applied after every two plies to reduce voidage in the specimens. The commercial autoclave was used for curing the panels of the stacked pre-preg. Temperature and pressure was controlled during the autoclave process. In the first minute of the process the vacuum bag was pressurised and the overpressure of 0.7 MPa was introduced in the autoclave and kept constant throughout the whole process. The temperature regime was programmed in the autoclave and it was controlled by four thermocouples mounted to the steel tool. The temperature rise of 2K per minute was realised. The dwell of 75 minutes at 90°C was applied in order to equalise the temperature in the stack. The curing at temperature of 120°C was realised over 60 min. Afterwards the stack was cooled down with the autoclave (approx. 0.6K per minute). Specimens were cut from cured panel using a diamond wheel. The edges of the specimens were polished. The dimensions of the specimens are given in Table 1. Fig. 1 presents the schematic of the specimen tested in four-point bending.

Fig.1 Schematic of the specimen with strain gauge and AE sensor (dimensions in mm).

The tests were carried out on a hydraulic SCHENK PSB 100 test machine operating under displacement control with a test rate of 0.03 mm/sec. The specimens were all fitted with strain gauges on both inner and outer radii at the centre of the curved section. In addition, a broadband acoustic emission transducer WD (Physical Acoustic Corp.) was mounted on the top surface of the specimen. Good contact of the sensor with the specimen was enforced by application of special surface paste. A picture of test arrangement is shown in Fig. 2. Following parameters were recorded during the test for all specimens:

- Loading and displacement of the grips of the hydraulic test machine,
- Strain gauge readings at bottom and top of each specimen,
- AE signals from the broadband transducer.

During the course of the test the AE signals were sensed by the broadband transducer and recorded by the PC based MISTRAS 2001 system [6]. The signal filtering at threshold of 45 dB(A) was used for all specimens. The analysis of recorded AE signals gave many parameters, including hits, counts, duration, amplitude, and others, that bring valuable information of the damage processes progressing during the loading. The strain gauges were

connected through the bridge to the MISTRAS 2001 system. The loading and displacement were also read from the SCHENK PSB 100 machine and recorded in real time in the MISTRAS 2001 system. This later allowed the correlation analysis of all the parameters recorded during the test.

Fig. 2 Picture presenting specimen fixed in the testing machine.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

All specimens failed suddenly with no prior visible damage. Failure occurred at the uppermost interface between the 0 plies and the ± 45 plies in all cases. The delamination propagated rather symmetrically in all specimens, however some lack of symmetry was evident due to not exactly symmetrical placement of the specimens in the grips. Large deflections (approximately 7 mm at failure) were noted in the curved section of the specimens. The AE sensor remained stable during the tests allowing the analysis of the AE signals.

The dimensions of specimens and results of the bending tests are given in the Table 1. The average specimen width and thickness were 19,36 mm and 4,09 mm respectively, with very small differences between the specimens. The strains at failure averaged for all specimens were 20 981,78 microstrain at bottom and -14 955,75 microstrain at the top of specimen. This gives the strain ration of 1,4. The average failure load for five specimens was -2.401,76 N.

Table 1. The results of bending tests

Test no.	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Max Strain [microstrain]		Max Load [N]
1	19,67	4,02	23 632,50	-15 611,25	-2 483,80
2	19,02	4,02	22 166,30	-16 272,50	-2 450,80
3	18,82	4,09	21 016,30	-14 978,75	-2 281,10
4	19,61	4,15	18 888,80	-13 397,50	-2 384,80
5	19,70	4,17	19 205,00	-14 518,75	-2 408,30
Mean	19,36	4,09	20 981,78	-14 955,75	-2 401,76
Stn. Dev.	0,41	0,07	1 998,01	1 093,52	77,50

Detailed analysis of specimen number 1 that has been chosen as the most representative one (out of five) is given below. Fig. 3 presents the selected parameters characterising the damage process during the testing of the representative specimen. Fig. 3a shows the strain gauge readings at the top (compressive) and the bottom (tensile) of the specimen. It is clearly visible that the lines representing the strains as function of time exhibit some degree of nonlinearity. This effect noticeable for other specimen too, is believed to be resulting from the geometrical nonlinearity of the specimen, as its curvature opens up under load. The same behaviour can be seen from the curve of loading versus time of test.

Fig. 3b presents both load and cumulated AE hits during the test. During the first 60 seconds of the test there is no AE activity recorded, which means that the acoustic activity during that time was below the threshold of 45 dB(A). Later the AE intensity is almost constant with short periods of higher or lower activity. This goes until 335 seconds after the beginning of test when there is a rapid increase of the AE hits recorded until the macroscopic failure that happens in the 351 second of the test. That moment at 335 second easily characterised by the inflexion point on the cumulated AE hits curve depicts the onset of the delamination process: 32 cumulated AE hits and -2 375.40 N of load (96% of maximal load).

Similar type of information is presented in the next two pictures. Fig. 3c visualises the distribution of the cumulated hits and counts during the test. There are several AE signals that exceed the value of 20 counts during the test (marked as squares), with majority of them in the first 200 seconds of the test. Fig. 3d shows the distribution of amplitude and cumulated amplitude of AE signals during the course of test. The AE events of the amplitude in the range of 45 - 55 dB(A) are present throughout the whole test. In the middle part of the test there are several AE events of higher amplitude in range of 65 to 75 dB(A) and of higher number of counts. The AE events that are characterised by 20 or more counts have the amplitude of more than 60 dB(A). These events do not incline any major damages that could determine the initiation of the damage leading to macroscopic failure. They are rather some very local effects (like fibre debonding) that happen while increasing the load and are caused by local pre-stressing and/or local imperfections induced during the curing of the laminate. The AE activity increases just before the failure of the specimen, which is evident by large number of events recorder within short period of time. These events have rather small number of counts and their amplitude is within the range of 45-55 dB(A). This is the behaviour observed in all other specimens.

Fig. 3e presents an attempt to correlate some parameters characterising the AE events recorded during the test, in this case it is the amplitude and duration of the AE event. The primary axis denotes the cumulated amplitude (line) and secondary axis represents the amplitude (dots). In the beginning of the test the AE events are of small amplitude and short duration, which increase with the time of test. The events reaching the highest amplitude and longest duration are the ones in the middle of the test. The events at the final stages of the test are becoming lower in amplitude and shorter in duration. This "loop" effect is repeated in all the specimens tested. The AE signals recorded between delamination onset and macroscopic failure are very similar one to another as they are falling into very narrow range of values of given parameters. In the picture the AE signals presented by dots overlay one another.

The amplitude and counts of AE events as a function of time are given in the Fig. 3f in the form of a three-dimensional graph. This picture visualises in a comprehensive way the most important parameters (counts and amplitude) that characterise the behaviour of the specimen during the test.

Fig. 3g and 3h present the waveform (voltage in mV versus time in microseconds) and the frequency spectra (amplitude in dB(A) versus frequency in kHz) of the AE signal registered just before the macroscopic damage of the specimen. The AE signal presented here is definitely a burst type and each event can be treated independently, however a small amount of continuous AE signal can be observed. This waveform is representative for the other several signals that have been registered between 335 and 351 seconds after the beginning of the test, which is the time window when the delamination propagates.

Fig. 3 The experimental results of specimen no.1: (a) strains at top and bottom of specimen versus time; (b) AE hits and load versus time; (c) cumulated hits and counts versus time; (d) cumulated amplitude and amplitude versus time; (e) amplitude versus duration; (f) counts and amplitude versus time (3D plot); (g) waveform and (h) frequency spectra of AE event before macroscopic failure.

Based on the analysis of experimental results the increase of AE parameters at level of 96% of maximal load can be chosen as criteria for determination of the critical load. All AE parameters have been chosen into account during the analysis. Hits, counts and amplitude of AE signals show the biggest change during the test, and therefore best describe the onset of the delamination.

The analysis of the experimental results of specimen no. 1 selected as most representative for the set of five specimens tested has been presented in this section of the paper. Several characteristics of the damage processes during the course of the experiment have been presented. The strains and loading do not change throughout the test in a way that information on the damage cumulation and progression can be obtained. However, the AE parameters and waveforms registered throughout the loading change their characteristics until macroscopic failure in a way that the determination of damage process prior to catastrophic failure is possible. The counts and amplitude of AE events give the most valuable information about the behaviour of the loaded specimen. Application of the AE measurements allowed determination of the delamination onset in a straightforward manner.

DISCUSSION

The approach for analysis of AE signals and other parametric data measured during the test as presented in a previous section has been applied to all five specimens. The onset of delamination process was clearly depicted on the curves presenting the distribution of AE signal throughout the test. The counts and amplitude of the AE events have been the most informative in case of all specimens. The results of analysis for each specimen are summarised and presented in the Table 2.

Table 2. The results of the delamination onset as predicted by the EA.

Test no.	Delamination Onset			Macroscopic Failure			Load Ratio
	Bottom Strain	Top Strain	Load	Bottom Strain	Top Strain	Load	
	[microstr]	[microstr]	[N]	[microstr]	[microstr]	[N]	
1	22 396.30	-14 835.00	-2 375.40	23 632.50	-15 611.25	-2 483.80	0.96
2	20 843.80	-15 295.00	-2 309.40	22 166.30	-16 272.50	-2 450.80	0.94
3	20 240.00	-14 432.50	-2 201.00	21 016.30	-14 978.75	-2 281.10	0.96
4	18 227.50	-12 966.25	-2 309.40	18 888.80	-13 397.50	-2 384.80	0.97
5	18 687.50	-14 087.50	-2 337.60	19 205.00	-14 518.75	-2 408.30	0.97
Mean	20 079.02	-14 323.25	-2 306.56	20 981.78	-14 955.75	-2 401.76	0.96
StnDev	1 684.12	882.49	64.93	1998.01	1093.52	77.50	0.01

* Strain given in microstrains [microstr].

The moment when the delamination starts to propagate has been determined from the distribution of counts and amplitude of AE events. That time point has been then related to the other parameters allowing presentation of the delamination onset by other parameters. In the Table 2 the onset of the delamination is given in terms of strains and load. The strains at failure initiation averaged for all specimens were 20 079,02 microstrain and -14 323,25 microstrain for bottom and top of specimen respectively. The loading was -2 306,56 N which is 96% of the failure load. The results of the analysis present high consistency.

The detailed analysis of the experimental results has been given in the previous section for selected representative specimen. The analyses of other specimens have been performed in a similar way and some interesting findings are presented in this section. A comparison of the selected AE parameters for three specimens is given in Fig. 4. The counts and cumulated counts as well as amplitude and cumulated amplitude of AE events are compared for the specimens 1,4 and 5 respectively. The propagating delamination is evident by increase of AE activity, that is characteristic by the value of AE counts (lower than 20) and relatively low

amplitude (45-70 dB(A)). This is a first type of phenomenon that can be observed in the specimen 1 and 4. However, the specimen no. 5 presents rather different behaviour before the failure. There are two "strong" AE events recorded just before the macroscopic failure that are characteristic by their large number of counts (57 and 70) and high amplitude (75 and 87 dB(A) respectively). These two events determine the behaviour of the specimen and are responsible for the failure. This second type of phenomenon has been found only in specimen no. 5. It is worth noticing that there is one AE event of amplitude of 92 dB(A) recorded at 215 second on the test. Judging by its parameters that AE event is most likely related to a fibre breaks. The waveform and frequency spectra of that AE event are given in the Fig. 6. The increase of AE activity typical for all other specimens is not quite present in this specimen and it may be concluded that it has been dominated by the small number of "strong" AE events. Further experiments are needed to validate the existence of the two types of behaviour prior to failure as discovered in this work.

Fig. 4 The AE signals as measured during the test. Counts and cumulated counts (left) and amplitude and cumulated amplitude (right) for specimens 1,4 and 5 respectively.

As it has been described previously in this paper the propagation of delamination is characterised by an intensive AE activity in all specimens except specimen no. 5, where there is a small number of "strong" AE events present. The waveform (voltage in mV versus time in microseconds) and the frequency spectra (amplitude in dB(A) versus frequency in kHz) of a typical AE event registered just before the macroscopic damage of the specimen is presented in the Fig. 5. The dominant frequencies of that event are the 100, 220, 400 and 500 kHz. This is a typical delamination type of discrete AE event, that is representative for all the events recorded between the onset of delamination and macroscopic failure of the specimen.

Fig. 5 The waveform and frequency spectra of the AE event recorded during the delamination propagation in specimen no. 4.

The experiments described in this paper show that behaviour of specimens after the delamination onset is characteristic by large number of AE events of relatively low amplitude and small number of counts. The exception to that behaviour is the specimen no. 5 that presents:

- Fibre break type of AE event prior to delamination onset (63 counts and 92 dB(A)),
- Small number of AE events of high amplitude and high number of counts (two events of 75 and 87 dB(A), and, 57 and 70 counts respectively).

The waveform and frequency spectra of the fibre break type of AE event in specimen no. 5 is presented in the Fig. 6. This AE event is very different to the ones representative for the delamination as presented above. It has longer duration (over 2000 microseconds), has many counts (63) and its amplitude is high (92 dB(A)) as compared to typical delamination type of AE event characterised by duration not exceeding 500 microseconds, number of counts below 20 and amplitude not higher than 70 dB(A).

Fig. 6: The waveform and frequency spectra of the AE event recognised as fibre breaks in specimen no. 5.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the results of four-point bending test carried out on 32-ply curved glass fibre/epoxy composite laminate of $(0_4/\pm 45_6)_s$ lay-up and their analysis as presented in this paper the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The AE parameters and waveforms registered throughout the test change their characteristics until macroscopic failure in a way that the determination of damage process prior to catastrophic failure is possible.
- Many parameters of AE events have been recorded and analysed. The analysis shows that counts and amplitude are best suitable for determination of damage initiation process as their characteristics change most significantly throughout the course of test.
- Two types of behaviour recorded by AE sensor during the delamination propagation has been observed with four samples providing intensive AE activity of relatively small amplitude and short events and one sample giving small number but "strong" AE events.
- The fibre breaks type of AE event has been recorded before the failure in one specimen. This type of AE event is very different to the typical delamination type of AE event as observed in all samples.
- Delamination onset at 96% of failure load has been determined thanks to application of AE during the static four-point bending test of curved composite beam. The obtained results show relatively high consistency.
- The application of AE testing has proved to be a good method for analysing the dynamic behaviour of the materials where other traditional methods do not give satisfactory results.
- This method can be applied in industrial practice for real-time monitoring of damage accumulation in structural components.

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